

Legends of Supplemental Figures

Supplemental Table 1. A) Schematic representation of target sgRNA sequences for specific Bag-1 gene loci. Different sgRNA sequences of Bag-1 KO plasmid (sc-417179) was obtained from Santa Cruz and the regions were found from comparing the human nucleotides sequences through BLAST and also checked at Bag-1 genomic sequence (NG_029018.1). B) Designed primers to validate Bag-1 deficiency in MCF-7 cells.

Supplemental Figure 1A-B-C. Each of the gRNAs caused deletions on both alleles that were observed by reverse reads of Sanger sequencing results.

Supplemental Figure 2. The overexpression of Bag-1 was confirmed by the immunoblotting assay.

Supplemental Figure 3. The expression profiles of 39 different RTKs of Path Scan RTK assay were analyzed by GraphPad Prism.

Supplemental Figure 4. The effect of Bag-1 KO on Akt phosphorylation and actin disruption in different MCF-7 Bag-1 KO clones was investigated. A) The petri dishes and morphological images of different MCF-7 cells models was obtained by light microscopy. MCF-7 wt, Control KO and Bag-1 KO Clone 12 were used in this study and Bag-1 KO Clone 10 and 11 was selected according to the Figure 1 Bag-1 expression level results. B) p-Akt (Ser 473), α -actinin and FAK expression levels were obtained by immunoblotting assay. GAPDH was used as a loading control.

Supplemental Figure 5. Confirmations of Bag-1 KO studies were performed in another breast cancer cell line MDA-MB-231. A) The petri dishes and morphological images of different MDA-MB-231 cells models was obtained by light microscopy. Control KO cells were generated by transfection of Control CRISPR/Cas9 Knockout plasmid (sc-418922). Bag-1 KO MDA-MB-231 cells were generated by co-transfection of Bag-1 CRISPR/Cas9 Knockout plasmid (sc-417179) and Bag-1 Homology Directed Repair plasmid (sc-417179-HDR) into MDA-MB-231 cells. To investigate the knockdown effect of Bag-1, MDA-MB-231 cells were transfected by Bag-1 shRNA plasmid (sc-29211-SH) and for control shRNA was transfected into MDA-MB-231 cells as mentioned in our previous paper [1]. B) Bag-1, p-Akt (Ser 473) and α -actinin expression levels were obtained by immunoblotting assay. GAPDH was used as a loading control.

Supplemental Figure 6. The cell viability of Bag-1 KO cells and transfected with Bag-1 S, M and L isoform respectively was determined by MTT Cell Viability assay.

Supplemental Figure 7. Visualization of actin cytoskeleton in Bag-1 isoform plasmid transfected MCF-7 wt and Bag-1 KO cells through fluorescent-labeled Phalloidin incubation by immunofluorescence experiment described in "Material and methods". This figure includes the same images with Figure 6b with high resolution.

Reference

- [1] P. O. Kilbas, I. M. Akcay, G. D. Doganay, and E. D. Arisan, "Bag-1 silencing enhanced chemotherapeutic drug-induced apoptosis in MCF-7 breast cancer cells affecting PI3K/Akt/mTOR and MAPK signaling pathways," *Mol. Biol. Rep.*, vol. 46, no. 1, pp. 847–860, 2019.